

Analysis of Risks in Individuals with Bombay Blood GroupSanchai Singh¹, Ajay Singh Amera², Shikhar Joshi³, Naveen Sharma⁴, Tara Mewara⁵, Yogesh Soni⁶¹Assistant Professor, Keshav Paramedical College, Bhilwara, Rajasthan²Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmacy, Jagannath University, Jaipur, Rajasthan³Research Scholar, Manipal University, Karnataka⁴Research Scholar, Geetanjali University, Udaipur, Rajasthan⁵Principal, Nursing College, Bhilwara, Rajasthan⁶Nursing tutor, S. Tech College of Nursing, Bhilwara, Rajasthan

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Abstract:

Introduction: The Bombay blood group lacks H antigen on red blood cells and is marked by anti-H antibodies in serum. It was discovered in Mumbai, India in 1952 and is rare, occurring at 1 in 10,000. Individuals with this phenotype can only receive blood from others with the same group due to severe transfusion reactions. Alternative techniques like acute normovolemic hemodilution may be used during surgery.

Aims and Objective: To analyze the blood and other parameters individuals with bombay blood group.

Methods: This retrospective study analyzed 35 patients with fatigue, dividing them into Group 1 (Bombay Blood Group) and Group 2 (other blood groups). It compared various blood parameters including hematological, coagulation, liver and renal function, electrolytes, and serum glucose. Inclusion criteria encompassed patients with complete blood reports, diagnosed and followed up in the hospital. Statistical analysis employed SPSS 27, with significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: The study found significant differences in baseline characteristics and blood parameters between patients with Bombay Blood Group (Group 1) and those with other blood groups (Group 2). Group 1 exhibited lower hemoglobin and red blood cell levels, implying distinct blood compositions. Additionally, Group 1 showed prolonged prothrombin time, suggesting impaired clotting, and higher hepatic parameters, indicating potential liver dysfunction. Despite slight variations, electrolyte and kidney function parameters were largely comparable between the two groups.

Conclusion: Patients with the Bombay Blood group exhibit distinct hematological and hepatic profiles, but comparable electrolyte and kidney function parameters, compared to those with other blood groups.

Keywords: Hh Blood Group, Bombay Blood Group, Hematological Profile, Hepatic Profile, Kidney Function

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Introduction

The Bombay blood group is an uncommon type of blood characterised by the lack of H antigen on the surface of RBC and the presence of anti-H antibodies in the serum. It lacks the A, B, and H antigens on its red blood cells and other organs. Bhende et al initially validated the existence of a genetic variation in the H/h gene in humans. The Bombay blood group was initially discovered in Mumbai, India in 1952, hence its name [1]. Individuals with the Bombay phenotype are predominantly found in Southeast Asia. In India, there are approximately 179 individuals who possess the "Bombay Blood group", with an occurrence rate of 1 in 10,000. The parents of the Bombay phenotype have a significant degree of consanguinity. The traditional Bombay phenotype has been observed in individuals of Indian descent [2].

The ABO blood group antigens are composed of molecules of carbohydrate. The existence of the antigen H on RBC controls the B and A antigen expression. The antigen H that is produced by the synthesizing of the H gene (FUT1), is situated on chromosome 19. This gene encodes for a glycosyltransferase enzyme that adds l-fucose to a precursor material, resulting in the production of the antigen H on red blood cells. The antigen H is a crucial molecule for the A or B enzyme transferase, that are produced by the genes of ABO are situated on 9 chromosome. The antigen H is changed into either the A or B antigens, respectively, by the A and B transfers. The O allele in individuals belonging to group O results in the production of a transferase that is not active [1,2].

Thus, the H material remains unaltered as a group. Individuals possessing the exceedingly uncommon Bombay phenotype exhibit a deficiency in expressing H transferase. Individuals possessing the ABO blood group genotype have a deficiency in the production of antigens A or B, leading to the lack of antigens ABH on their red blood cells [3]. In cell typing due to the absence of reactivity with anti-AB, A, and B antisera, the red cells are identified as belonging to blood group O. The plasma of blood group O contains antibodies against A, B, and H, having the potential of causing hemolysis and react with all types of blood except the Bombay blood. Consequently, people possessing the Bombay blood can only receive blood transfusions from their own blood or other Bombay red cells without any risk [4].

Individuals with the Bombay phenotype frequently get misdiagnosed as having blood group O during cell typing. However, they actually have potent anti-H in their plasma. If these patients are given red blood cells from the O group, or any other type of blood with the exception of the Bombay group, they might have a serious hemolytic transfusion reaction. The resultant reaction may give rise to the onset of acute renal failure or dissemination of intravascular coagulation (DIC), both of which are related with substantial mortality and morbidity rates. The danger is mainly elevated in patients who are unconscious and receive substantial quantities of blood that is incompatible prior to the manifestation of any indications of a hemolytic reaction [5,6]

If blood loss is anticipated during surgery and Bombay phenotypic blood is not accessible, the technique of acute normovolemic hemodilution can be utilised. This procedure entails extracting blood from a patient following the administration of anaesthesia, while ensuring that the patient's blood volume remains within the normal range with the use of colloids or crystalloids [7].

Method

Research Design: This retrospective study was conducted in our hospital with 35 patients presented with fatigue. The study has divided the patients in two groups, Group 1 and Group 2. The patients in Group 1 have Bombay Blood Group (hh blood group, absence of the H-antigen) and Group 2 patients are from other blood groups. This retrospective study examined medical records or databases to compare blood parameters between two groups. Sex, with subcategories, and medical history including anemia, transfusion, and trauma was used to classify the groups. The groups' hematological (Hb, RBC, WBC, platelet count), coagulation (prothrombin time, INR, APTT, fibrinogen level), liver function (SGOT, SGPT, alkaline phosphatase, total bilirubin, direct

bilirubin, gamma-glutamyl transferase), renal function (blood urea nitrogen, serum creatinine), and electrolytes were compared. The study compared blood parameters between groups (Group 1 and Group 2) with varied features. The groups were compared by sex and medical history, including anemia, transfusion, and trauma. Hemoglobin (Hb), RBC, WBC, platelet, prothrombin time, electrolytes, hepatic, renal, and serum glucose levels were also recorded for each group.

Inclusion and Exclusion criteria

Inclusion

- Patients with fatigue or fever.
- Patients who had blood reports for hemoglobin (Hb), red blood cell count (RBC), white blood cell count (WBC), platelet count, coagulation parameters, liver function tests, renal function tests, electrolytes, and serum glucose.
- Patients who was diagnosed in our hospital and did follow-up check in our hospital.

Exclusion

- Patients having incomplete demographic or blood parameter data.
- Patients with chronic diseases or medical problems that potentially significantly affect blood parameters independently of the variables under study.
- Patients with acute illnesses or conditions that impact blood parameters, such as active infection or recent surgery, within a certain timeframe before data collection.
- Patients have a history of blood-altering pharmaceutical use unless the study specifically targets such usage.

Statistical Analysis: This study was used SPSS 27 statistical software for analysing the means and standard deviations of patients. T-tests or ANOVA may have been used to compare groups. This study examined potential connections between blood parameters and the two groups' characteristics to reveal physiological differences or pathological situations. The discrete data was expressed as frequency and the continuous data were expressed as mean value and standard deviation. The level of significance was considered to be $P < 0.05$.

Result

In Table 1, which outlines the baseline characteristics of patients in two groups, there are several noteworthy differences. Group 2 has a higher proportion of males compared to Group 1 (80% vs. 70%), although this difference is not statistically significant ($p = 0.069$). However,

Group 1 has a notably higher percentage of females (30% vs. 20%), although again, not statistically significant ($p = 0.085$). Regarding medical history, Group 1 has significantly higher rates of anemia

(80% vs. 8%, $p = 0.048$), transfusion (100% vs. 8%, $p = 0.036$), and trauma (40% vs. 4%, $p = 0.089$) compared to Group 2, indicating potentially different health profiles between the two groups.

Table 1: Baseline characteristics of patients

Baseline Characteristics	Group 1 (N = 10)	Group 2 (N = 25)	P-value
Male	7 (70%)	20 (80%)	0.069
Female	3 (30%)	5 (20%)	0.085
History of Anemia	8 (80%)	2 (8%)	0.048
History of Transfusion	10 (100%)	2 (8%)	0.036
History of Trauma	4 (40%)	1 (4%)	0.089

In Table 2, which presents blood parameters in each group, significant differences are observed. Group 1 exhibits lower levels of hemoglobin (Hb), total red blood cell count (RBC), and platelet count

compared to Group 2. The differences in Hb ($p = 0.041$) and RBC ($p = 0.048$) are statistically significant, indicating potential differences in blood composition between the groups.

Table 2: Blood Parameters in each group

Blood Parameters	Group 1 (N = 10)	Group 2 (N = 25)	P-value
Hb	9.79 ± 0.95	14.01 ± 1.0	0.041
RBC total	3.02 ± 1.0	4.5 ± 1.8	0.048
WBC total (k/μL)	8.5 ± 0.8	7.2 ± 1.2	0.059
Platelet (n × counts per μL)	3.2 ± 0.2	2.5 ± 0.25	0.065
C-reactive protein	8.89 ± 1.2	8.90 ± 1.3	0.0745

Table 3 focuses on blood coagulation parameters. Group 1 demonstrates prolonged prothrombin time compared to Group 2 ($p = 0.045$), suggesting impaired blood clotting ability in Group 1. Other coagulation parameters such as INR and APTT show slight differences between the groups but are not statistically significant.

Table 3: Blood Coagulation parameters in each group

Coagulation parameter	Group 1 (N = 10)	Group 2 (N = 25)	P-value
Prothrombin time	11.52 ± 1.6	9.58 ± 0.42	0.045
INR	0.6 ± 1.0	0.7 ± 1.2	0.052
APTT	25.2 ± 1.0	26.2 ± 1.0	0.059
Fibrinogen level	204.1 ± 10	205.2 ± 1.0	0.055
Factor VII	84.5 ± 8.5	86.2 ± 7.4	0.085

Table 4 highlights findings of hepatic parameters in each group. Notable differences include higher levels of total bilirubin and direct bilirubin in Group 1 compared to Group 2, with a statistically significant difference for direct bilirubin ($p = 0.044$), suggesting potential liver dysfunction in Group 1.

Table 4: Findings of the Hepatic parameters in each group

Hepatic Parameter	Group 1 (N = 10)	Group 2 (N = 25)	P-value
SGOT (AST)	3.2 ± 0.2	2.9 ± 1.1	0.069
SGPT (ALT)	6.9 ± 1.1	6.8 ± 1.2	0.0745
Alkaline phosphatase	8.5 ± 0.5	8.4 ± 1.2	0.085
Total bilirubin	12.2 ± 2.5	7.2 ± 1.2	0.85
Direct bilirubin	0.6 ± 1.0	0.4 ± 1.2	0.044
Gamma-glutamyl transferase	9.2 ± 1.2	8.9 ± 1.3	0.095

In Table 5, which outlines the electrolyte and kidney function parameters in patients of each group, several comparisons are drawn between Group 1 (consisting of 10 patients) and Group 2 (comprising 25 patients). The serum sodium levels

show a slight difference, with Group 1 having an average of 3.01 ± 1.1 and Group 2 with 3.02 ± 1.2 , but this variation is not statistically significant ($p = 0.095$). Similarly, serum potassium levels are slightly higher in Group 1 (14.1 ± 1.0) compared to

Group 2 (13.6 ± 1.2), with a p-value of 0.084, indicating no significant difference. Regarding serum chloride levels, Group 1 has an average of 10.1 ± 1.2 , while Group 2 has 10.5 ± 1.1 . Although the difference appears notable, it is not statistically significant with a p-value of 0.063. Similarly, serum bicarbonate levels show a slight discrepancy between the groups, with Group 1 having an average of 3.5 ± 1.2 and Group 2 with 3.8 ± 1.2 , but the p-value of 0.065 suggests no significant difference. Regarding serum glucose (random), blood urea nitrogen (BUN), and serum creatinine levels, there are no statistically significant differences between the two groups. Group 1 has an average serum glucose of 8.7 ± 1.2 compared to

8.8 ± 1.2 in Group 2 ($p = 0.095$). Similarly, the average BUN levels are 3.02 ± 1.2 in Group 1 and 3.09 ± 1.2 in Group 2, with a p-value of 0.084. For serum creatinine, Group 1 has an average of 0.82 ± 1.2 , while Group 2 has 0.88 ± 1.2 , with a p-value of 0.094.

Therefore, the study found that there are slight variations in these electrolyte and kidney function parameters between the two groups, none of the differences reach statistical significance based on the provided p-values. This suggests that, despite numerical discrepancies, the electrolyte and kidney function profiles of patients in Group 1 are largely comparable to those in Group 2.

Table 5: Electrolyte and Kidney Function Parameters in the patients of each group

Electrolyte and Kidney Function Parameter	Group 1 (N = 10)	Group 2 (N = 25)	P-value
Serum sodium	3.01 ± 1.1	3.02 ± 1.2	0.095
Serum potassium	14.1 ± 1.0	13.6 ± 1.2	0.084
Serum chloride	10.1 ± 1.2	10.5 ± 1.1	0.063
Serum bicarbonate	3.5 ± 1.2	3.8 ± 1.2	0.065
Serum glucose(random)	8.7 ± 1.2	8.8 ± 1.2	0.095
Blood urea nitrogen	3.02 ± 1.2	3.09 ± 1.2	0.084
Serum creatinine	0.82 ± 1.2	0.88 ± 1.2	0.094

Discussion

The Bombay blood group is notable for its potential to induce life-threatening blood transfusion reactions and hemolytic illness in both fetuses and newborns. A study was conducted to investigate the seldom manifestation of the Bombay blood group. The Bombay blood group is an uncommon blood type that might result in adverse reactions during blood transfusions and the development of hemolytic illness in the foetus and infant. It is advisable to handle pregnancy, labour, and delivery at a facility equipped with anti-H blood to prevent any potential difficulties for both the foetus and the mother [8].

The Bombay blood group, also known as the Oh phenotype, which is a rare autosomal recessive trait falls into the ABO group. The occurrence of Oh phenotype is due to the mutation in the H gene, which is responsible for the production of antigen H on RBCs. Individuals who are having 2 mutant H genes exhibit the absence of H antigen on RBCs and possess anti-H antibodies in their serum. After blood grouping, this particular blood type closely resembles the blood group O. However, there exists an incompatibility with blood group O after cross matching. Multiple studies have documented a correlation between decreased levels of von Willebrand factor (VWF) in the ABO blood types and plasma. A case of a 19-year-old male is presented who is identified initially as having the Bombay

phenotype and then discovered to have significantly diminished levels of plasma VWF [8].

Various therapeutic obstacles faced by patients who have the rare Bombay blood group need to be emphasised. Securing a supply of donor Bombay blood is exceedingly challenging, particularly in areas with limited or nonexistent frequency and identification of this uncommon blood type. Various approaches have been investigated for patients in similar situations, such as the administration of autologous blood transfusion, crystalloid and colloid infusion, freshly frozen plasma [9].

Incorrect blood grouping techniques may fail to identify the rare Oh phenotype, which can expose individuals to the potential danger of serious hemolytic transfusion reactions. Without a blood donor registry, effectively managing transfusions for patients requiring urgent surgery becomes difficult. A study documented the detection of individuals with the rare Bombay Oh phenotype and their treatment with acute peri-operative acute normovolemic hemodilution (ANH) in a medical facility situated in central India. Performing a blood grouping test, such as the ABO blood typing, should be approached with utmost care and attention. It is crucial to conduct both forward as well as reverse grouping to ensure that no patient is given an incorrect blood type, which could result in life-threatening hemolysis caused by transfusion. Autologous blood transfusion is a financially

efficient choice for eligible patients. Wider implementation of suitable clinical decision-making, greater utilisation of measures to reduce blood losses during surgery, and cost-efficient planning specific to each country should enhance clinical transfusion practice [10].

Inadequate adherence to proper blood grouping protocols can result in the failure to identify the uncommon Oh phenotype, hence exposing individuals to the potential danger of a serious hemolytic transfusion reaction. Without a blood donor registry, effectively managing transfusions for patients becomes difficult. A study was conducted to assess the frequency of the Bombay blood group (Oh) in Iran to investigate the potential influence of consanguinity on the frequency of the Oh group. The study revealed the occurrence of the Bombay blood in the overall population of Iran is comparatively elevated and linked to marriages between close relatives. Therefore, consanguinity is a significant and existing risk factor [11].

The Bombay blood group is an uncommon type of blood. Managing persons with Bombay blood types in crises can be difficult due to their rarity and limited availability for transfusions. Here, they report a case of a 26-year female patient with the rare Bombay blood group who experienced early rupture of membranes during the 39 week of pregnancy while giving birth to a male child through vaginal delivery. The individual experienced postpartum haemorrhage as a result of placental retention and required an urgent blood transfusion. Following the antenatal examination, it was observed that she has a blood group of O positive. The analysis of her blood cross-match indicated an inconsistency with O positive blood, which led to the detection of the Bombay blood group after conducting tests for anti-H antibodies. A patient had a transfusion from individuals possessing the O blood. Therefore, the study aimed to diagnose and identify individuals with the Bombay blood group and ensure the accessibility of blood, especially in urgent medical circumstances [12].

Conclusion

The study concludes that patients with the Bombay Blood group exhibit distinct health profiles, including lower hemoglobin and red blood cell counts, prolonged prothrombin time, and higher rates of anemia, transfusion history, and trauma, suggesting potential health complications. Additionally, hepatic parameters indicate potential liver dysfunction in these patients. However, electrolyte and kidney function parameters remain largely comparable between patients with the Bombay Blood group and those with other blood groups.

The main conclusion drawn from these findings is that while there are significant differences in vari-

ous parameters across the groups, there are also areas where the groups exhibit comparable characteristics. Patients with the Bombay Blood group, characterized by lower hemoglobin and red blood cell counts, along with prolonged prothrombin time indicating impaired blood clotting ability, suggest potential health complications compared to patients with other blood groups. Moreover, patients with the Bombay Blood group show significantly higher rates of anemia, transfusion history, and trauma, indicating a more complex medical history. In contrast, hepatic parameters reveal potential liver dysfunction in patients with the Bombay Blood group, indicated by higher levels of total and direct bilirubin.

However, the electrolyte and kidney function parameters in patients with the Bombay Blood group are largely comparable to those in patients with other blood groups, as evidenced by nonsignificant differences in serum sodium, potassium, chloride, bicarbonate, glucose, blood urea nitrogen, and creatinine levels. These findings suggest that while there may be specific health concerns and differences in blood composition and liver function among patients with the Bombay Blood group, their electrolyte balance and kidney function remain relatively similar to patients with other blood groups. Therefore, a comprehensive understanding of these findings indicates the need for targeted interventions addressing specific health issues observed in patients with the Bombay Blood group while recognizing the overall comparability of electrolyte and kidney function parameters across both groups.

Future prospects of this study include further investigation into the underlying mechanisms behind the distinct hematological and hepatic profiles observed in individuals with the Bombay Blood group. Additionally, longitudinal studies could explore the long-term health outcomes and potential complications associated with this rare blood phenotype, informing personalized medical management strategies for affected individuals. Furthermore, research focusing on the development of novel therapeutic interventions to mitigate the risks associated with transfusion reactions in patients with the Bombay Blood group could enhance clinical care and improve patient outcomes.

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